

A note on detection efficiency with a limited axial field of view of a nuclear fuel assembly

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1 Introduction

A common experimental setup used when performing axial scans of nuclear fuel assemblies, and in which gamma spectroscopy data is collected continuously over the scan, involves a collimator slit that limits the field of view for the detector, see e.g. references [2, 3, 5]. The purpose of the collimator is obvious; to measure the radiation emitted from a limited section of the object under study and in some cases to reduce the counting rate. Due to the limited field of view, Monte Carlo calculations of the detection efficiency can be simplified to not use the complete fuel assembly since a majority of the emitted radiation will not make it to the collimator slit. Using such simplification requires a correction of the calculated efficiency in studies that includes gamma radiation emitted from the whole fuel assembly. This note shows how such a correction can be performed when the axial source distribution is assumed uniform. An example is given where the correction was put into use and a short outlook with possible improvements is provided.

2 Assumptions

As a basis for discussion, two assumptions are made:

1. The detection efficiency ε_s of radiation emitted in one axial segment of the nuclear fuel assembly have already been determined, e.g. through a Monte Carlo type calculation.
2. The detection efficiency of any radiation emitted outside the axial segment is zero.

3 Detection efficiency

The efficiency of detecting radiation emitted from a nuclear fuel assembly, ε_f , is generally defined as in equation (1), where N is the number of quanta of interest. N_f is the number

of quanta emitted from the whole fuel assembly, N_d is the number of quanta detected. When the N 's are large enough, the ratio describes the probability of detecting one quanta emitted from the source.

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{N_d}{N_f} \quad (1)$$

Since we have defined a segment of the fuel assembly that is the emitting radiation source, it is natural to define a fraction f between the number of quanta emitted from this segment N_s compared to the number emitted from the whole of the assembly. Equation (2) defines this ratio.

$$f = \frac{N_s}{N_f} \quad (2)$$

The detection efficiency of the whole fuel assembly can be rewritten as in equation (3), remembering that N_d/N_s is the detection efficiency of the source segment, ε_s .

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{fN_d}{N_s} = f\varepsilon_s \quad (3)$$

4 Example

In reference [1], we have demonstrated the use of calculated detection efficiencies for a case when the activities of ^{137}Cs in pressurised water reactor type nuclear fuel assemblies are measured and compared with corresponding calculations. In this case, the photon flux at the detector was calculated based on a segment of the fuel assembly that had a height of about $56363 \mu\text{m}$. This height corresponds to the height of a segment in the center of the fuel assembly in the direct or optical field of view through the collimator slit used in the measurements, plus 5 cm.

It was assumed in this case that the fuel was somewhat axially symmetric in the sense that the fraction f of quanta emitted from the source segment was equal to the height of the segment relative to the whole length of the radiation emitting part of the fuel rods. I.e., the axial source distribution was assumed homogeneous and uniformly distributed.

The pellet stack in the fuel assemblies have a height of about 3.7 m, [4]. The fraction f as defined above is thus about 0.0152. In [1], the flux was calculated per emitted photon and was used as a detection efficiency since it was divided by the photon flux calculated from a point source used as a reference for the activity determination. Since [1] calculates the flux from the segment only, it was corrected by a fraction 0.0145 using a value of 3.88 m for the length of the fuel rods, to arrive at the fuel fuel assembly detection efficiency.

5 Discussion and outlook

A more detailed modeling can be performed for increased precision, e.g. dividing the fuel assembly into regions which can be considered piece-wise uniformly distributed and where the reasoning used in this note applied to each region. In such cases, ε_f would be the average of the corresponding detection efficiencies in the regions.

For cases when the form of the axial source distribution is known, a more accurate average detection efficiency calculation can be performed.

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References

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